

AMAZING BOOKS

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Abstract. The article provides interesting information about the most amazing and unique books in the world.

Аннотация. В статье представлена интересная информация о самых удивительных и уникальных книгах мира.

Keywords. Amazing books, the oldest, the largest and the most silent book, collection, woodcut, printing house.

Ключевые слова. Удивительные книги, самая старая, самая большая и самая тихая книга, коллекция, ксилография, типография.

The book has been a leader in information storage and distribution for many years and still remains so in many ways. Libraries in the world are a place of

knowledge and information, and they store the most popular and masterpieces. Today we present to your attention a list of the most amazing books in the world. Of course, most of them are also interesting to Uzbek readers.

The oldest book on earth was written in 3350 BC. This book, written on papyrus, was found in one of the temples of Thebes. Now this unique book is stored in the National Library of Paris. Sometimes such scrolls were very long. The Harris papyrus, kept in the British Museum, is about 45 meters long.

Ancient Assyria, the book was written on clay. The face of such a book page is 32x32 cm, 2.5 cm thick, and looks like a real flat brick. Books consist of tens, sometimes hundreds of such pages.

Books similar to today's books first appeared in the 1st century AD. They are made of wood. To make the page soft and smooth, melted wax is evenly poured over it. After the wax hardened, it was written on with a sharp metal stick. A number of such boards were collected and bound into a book.

Parchment was used as book pages in the city of Pergamum (Asia Minor) in the 2nd century BC. It was prepared as follows: calf or sheep skin was melted in a lime solution and then dried on a rack. After the dry skin is smoothed with sandpaper, honey is applied to it. A lot of calf skin was needed to make a thick book. Preparing a book and copying it required many months of work. Sometimes the parchment was used a second time. For this, previous writings on it were washed with milk or scraped with a knife. Anew was written on the cleaned parchment. Many rare books have been lost in this way.

One of the largest ancient books in terms of volume is "Sermons of Musha Monastery" written in Armenian. This manuscript weighing no less than two pounds (32 kilograms) was taken by the Seljuks in 1204.

Most of the texts were carved on trees using the method of xylography invented in the East. In Korea, China, and Japan, this method is V||| began to be used in the century. Tens of thousands of Buddhist texts were published in this way. The oldest xylographic book that has reached us is the book "Diamond Sutra" (the sacred and legal book of the ancient people of the Buddhist religion). This book, written in the Buddha text, was written in China in 868. It is now kept in the British Museum in London.

In 1899, in Warsaw, A.S. On the occasion of the hundredth anniversary of Pushkin's birth, his poem "Eugene Onegin" was published in 28\18 mm format. Each page of the booklet contains thirty words. A tiny book is muddled into a medallion. A lens for reading a book is placed in the center of the medallion cover.

In 1832, 100 copies of "Complex of English Heroes" were printed in London. It is 8 yards long and 4 yards wide (1 yard = 0.91 meters). The size of the letters is 0.5 feet (15 centimeters). This book is considered one of the largest books in the world.

A book containing 68 stories was published in Austria. Each story is printed on a different colored paper. 1934 American Calendar January and February on printed paper, March and April on papyrus paper, May and June on mosquito repellent paper, July and August on fly swatter sticky paper, September and October typewriter on colored paper, and November-December on filter paper. The book was also printed on silk and satin at various times. The material on which newspapers are printed has also changed. For example, in France, newspaper articles are printed on a thinly spread dough with a printer's edible ink.

Another

French newspaper is printed on thin rubber. It was easy to read while taking a bath. He could easily read a newspaper published in Spain even in the dark. Because his letters were shining. In England, cloth replaced newsprint. After reading such a newspaper, it was used as a handkerchief.

At the end of the 15th century, the famous Venetian publisher Aid Manutsi "invented" the printing of books in a reduced format. The Dutch Elzevir brothers, who lived in the 17th century, passed him. They began to publish volume after volume of collections of poems in a very small format. The world's smallest book has been published in Wooster, America. Its size is 6.3x4.5 mm, red morocco (animal skin) cover, 34 pages. This is a collection of poems by Omar Khayyam. The weight of the booklet is 64 g. The first miniature book printed in Russian is the 65x75 mm book "The Art of Dealing" (1788). In 1855, I. Krylov's book "Proverbs" was published in the size of a postage stamp. The poems in the booklet are typed in a microscopic letter - a diamond. The first small booklet published in the former Soviet Union was the "Constitution of the RSFSR" published in Kmeshma in 1921. Its size is 35x50 mm. There are 500 books with different titles in Moscow's Dwarf Book Fund. More than half of my works were published during the former Soviet Union. Pushkin's works are printed in more than 50 miniature books in the collection.

The book "Olympic Oath" published in the languages of the participating countries of the Olympic Games was published in Germany. This compact book is the size of a child's fingernail.

The most expensive book in the world today is the Leicester Codex, or Treatise on Water, Earth, and Heavenly Bodies. It was written by Leonardo da Vinci in Milan between 1506 and 1510. Bill Gates bought the manuscript 16 years ago for

his collection. He paid \$30.8 million for the Leicester Code. In this artifact, the texts are written by hand on the glass, which is unusual. You can read them only with a mirror. You can also see many drawings, mathematical calculations and pictures of genius in it.

Conclusion

Modern literature is rarely surprising. But ancient amazing books still amaze the whole world. A book is a ship of wisdom that travels in the sea of time and carries its precious cargo from generation to generation. will undoubtedly make him a thinker.

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